

Implementation of South Korea's Chanbogo Submarine Purchase Policy

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ABSTRACT: A strong national defense system does not require consideration of empathy, including the geographical factors of the country being examined, the national resources of a country, an analysis of possible threats that will arise, and the development of information technology. Defense is something that is fundamental to the survival of a country. Cooperation between Indonesia and South Korea in the defense industry is centered on the development of the changbogo class submarine and the development of the KFX / IFX fighter aircraft. Seen from the Government's policy, it can be seen that the domestic industry is unprepared to support the independence of the defense industry. This unpreparedness can be caused by the absence of supporting infrastructure or financial support for mass production of defense and security equipment. This scientific work is expected to provide recommendations in defense policy regarding submarine development. This study uses a scientific approach with qualitative descriptive methods and uses implementation theory by George C. Edward. The results of this study a policy review of South Korea's Submarine purchase policy . The conclusion of this study are constraints and challenges faced in improving submarines, particularly related to the ability of PT. PAL Indonesia is still limited in the manufacture of the DSME 209/1400 submarine.

KEYWORDS: National defense, maritime security, Communication, Submarine and Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

A strong national defense system does not require consideration of empathy, including the geographical factors of the country being examined, the national resources of a country, an analysis of possible threats that will arise, and the development of information technology. Defense is something that is fundamental to the survival of a country. Without a strong defense system, threats from outside parties will more easily disrupt the stability of the country. Therefore, various elements are needed to create a strong defense system. One of them is having a defense industry capable of meeting the needs of the armed forces. [1]

Cooperation in the defense sector that has existed between Indonesia and South Korea includes an agreement regarding implementation arrangements between the Ministry of Defense and Security of the Republic of Indonesia and the Defense Partnership of the Republic of South Korea regarding mutual acceptance of intergovernmental quality assurance for defense materials and services (Agreement Between the Department of Defense and Security of the Republic of Indonesia and the Ministry of National Defense of the Republic of Korea Concerning Mutual Acceptance of Government Quality Assurance of Defense Materiel and Services signed in Jakarta on October 7, 1999.[2]

Talking about the sea and its territory, the territory of Indonesia was first determined by the Territoriale Zee en Maritime Kringen Ordonantie (TZMKO) 19394. In the TZMKO, the Dutch government determined that the width of the sea belonging to Indonesia was only 3 nautical miles from the mainland [3]. Furthermore, the Government of Indonesia struggled for the concept of Archipelago Insight starting from the drafting of the concept in the Djuanda Declaration on December 13, 1957 which was later confirmed in Law No.4 / PRP of 1960 concerning Indonesian Waters [4].

Cooperation between Indonesia and South Korea in the defense industry is centered on the development of the changbogo class submarine and the development of the KFX / IFX fighter aircraft [5]. These two projects are the main focus of strategic cooperation between Indonesia and South Korea. Changbogo class submarines themselves have several cutting-edge technologies such as the Latest Combat System, Enhanced Operating System, Non-hull penetrating mast, and Comfortable Accommodation [6]. In this case, the purchase of the changbogo submarine has the aim of meeting the needs of the Indonesian Navy. [7]

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Seen from the Government's policy, it can be seen that the domestic industry is unprepared to support the independence of the defense industry. This unpreparedness can be caused by the absence of supporting infrastructure or financial support for mass production of defense and security equipment. Likewise problems in the industrial sector. If it is related to the roadmap for the development of defense and security equipment, is it able to provide assurance that the products to be produced are in accordance with the specifications desired by the TNI in terms of quality. If the quality of the products produced does not match the specifications required by the TNI, the needs for TNI operations will be disrupted and put the personnel in the field at risk.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The method used in this research is a qualitative method with literature study design and phenomenology. In qualitative research, the researcher must not influence the situation and social interactions between the researcher and the subject / informant being studied and even between the subjects studied. The interactions between the individuals studied should occur as they really are in the context, not engineering researchers.

The qualitative research method is also a research method that emphasizes in-depth understanding aspects of a problem rather than looking at the problem for generalization research. This research method prefers to use in-depth analysis techniques (indepth analysis), which examines the problem on a case-by-case basis because the qualitative methodology believes that the nature of one problem will be different from the nature of another problem.

This research uses descriptive qualitative method, the theory used is Implementation theory by George C. Edward III. Edward III's model is top down and suitable to be implemented at a structured bureaucratic level in a government institution, where each hierarchical level has a role in accordance with the function in the elaboration of policies to be implemented and facilitates the implementation of a policy at each bureaucratic level starting from the level of department (central government), up to the executive level in the field. [8]

Data Collection and Analysis

According to Moleong (2007), the source of qualitative research data is a display in the form of spoken or written words that are observed by researchers, and objects that are observed in detail so that the meaning implied in the document or object can be captured. The source of the data must be original, but if the original data is difficult to obtain, then photocopies or copies will not be a problem, as long as strong evidence of validation can be obtained.

The research method used is qualitative research methods. Qualitative research is research that prioritizes problems of process and meaning / perception, where this research is expected to reveal a variety of qualitative information with researched and meaningful descriptions, which also does not reject quantitative information in the form of numbers or quantities.[9]

The definition of research is an organized investigation, or a careful and critical investigation in finding facts to determine something. Researchers will collect various information data that is relevant and related to the research topic. In-depth information about the sea lanes owned by countries around the Southeast Asian waters, it is inevitable that this region is an important part of the world's maritime axis. Indonesia, which is an archipelago, has 39 straits that are interconnected with other straits in the Asian region. With such conditions, Indonesia actually becomes a barometer and even the key to regional stability.

In choosing sampling, researchers used purposive sampling method. Purposive sampling is carried out by considering subjects and objects that are considered representative as units of analysis based on research needs. Types of research methods can be classified based on, objectives, and natural setting of the object under study. Based on the objectives, research methods can be classified into basic research, applied research and research and development. Furthermore, based on the level of naturalness, research methods can be grouped into experimental, survey and naturalistic research methods. resource persons are selected with the consideration that they can correctly answer and know the existing phenomena related to state security as a maritime axis.[10]

Data collection was carried out through literature study. Discussion of problems and analysis is carried out through an in-depth literature process, which is then compiled into a comprehensive and in-depth report and analysis. Data collection techniques are the most strategic step in research, because the main purpose of research is to get data. Without knowing the data collection technique, the researcher will not get data that meets the established data standards.

Data collection can take place in a variety of steps and rules, multiple sources, and multiple ways. When viewed from the data source, data collection can use primary sources and secondary sources. Primary sources are data sources that directly provide data to data collectors, and secondary sources are sources that do not directly provide data to data collectors, for example through other people or through documents.

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3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The National Defense

State defense, also known as national defense, is all efforts to defend the sovereignty of the state, the territorial integrity of a country and the safety of the entire nation from threats and disturbances to the integrity of the nation and state. The concept of national security of the Republic of Indonesia is clearly and firmly recorded in paragraph IV of the preamble to the 1945 Constitution. Therefore, the government, with all its potential and resources, is obliged to maintain national security by:

1. Protect all citizens and all spilled Indonesian blood;
2. Promote general welfare and the intellectual life of the nation; and
3. To participate in carrying out world order based on eternal peace and social justice.[11]

State defense is carried out by the government and prepared early by the state defense system. National defense is a joint force (civil and military) held by a State to ensure the integrity of its territory, protection of people and / or safeguarding its interests. National defense is managed by the Ministry of Defense [12].

The Indonesian State Defense System is a defense system that is universal in nature which in this case involves all citizens, territories and other national resources, and is prepared early by the government and is carried out in a total, integrated, directed, and continuous manner to uphold state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and the safety of the entire nation from all threats[13].

In order to realize the vision of the World Maritime Axis Government, the Indonesian Navy as the main component of the state defense force at sea has endeavored to carry out the duties mandated by law through the national defense strategy at sea as outlined in the form of the Archipelago Marine Defense Strategy[14].

The SPLN owned by the Indonesian Navy which has been used since 2004 through Kasal Decree needs to be reviewed, whether this strategy has been able to realize the five pillars contained in the maritime axis. Therefore, the SPLN needs to be examined to what extent it is able to answer all the needs to realize the vision of Indonesia as a world maritime axis and be able to secure the ALKI area, or there needs to be renewal so that the SPLN can support the achievement of the five main pillars of the vision. The target of the SPLN is to prevent parties that have the potential to interfere with the sovereignty of the country and the territorial integrity of the Republic of Indonesia by sea[15].

3.2. Maritime Security

Maritime culture is an inseparable part of people's lives, especially those related to maritime and maritime affairs. Fishermen and coastal communities, for example, have local wisdom in managing and utilizing marine resources so that the sustainability of their livelihoods is guaranteed to their children and grandchildren. The huge maritime and marine potential should be utilized for the welfare of the community. However, in reality this potential has not been optimally utilized. This has contributed to the high poverty rate Security is basically an effort to manage threat elements with the ultimate goal of creating an environment in the state and at the individual level that is free from all forms of threats [16]

The communitarian understanding (reciprocity between individuals and their communities) which is mandated by the Preamble of the 1945 Indonesian Constitution, shows that the concept of a nation is human citizens of Indonesia (human). Thus people centered security (human security) in the Indonesian context is not referred to as individual security or mere human security but a reciprocal relationship that cannot be separated between citizen security as part of national security. Indonesia is the largest archipelagic country in the world with a coastline of approximately 81,000 km. Indonesia has more than 17,000 islands and its sea area covers 5.8 million km² or about 80% of the total area of Indonesia. In fact, Indonesia is an archipelagic state, the existence of Indonesia as an archipelagic country was recognized in 1982 through the United Nations convention on the law of the sea (UNCLOS). Maritime security is influenced by the actions and patterns of interaction between the actors involved. The maritime security concept lies between two ideas:

1. The group uses a traditional security framework,
2. groups using non-traditional frameworks.[17]

The emergence of maritime security issues begins with the function of territorial waters that are increasingly strategic for the interests of countries in the world. According to Susanto and Munaf (2014: 48-50), the maritime area is the main lifeblood of global economic interactions, thus making maritime security a crucial issue for many countries in the world. Maritime security stability is needed by all countries in the world in order to protect the national interests of the nation which have an impact on national development. Maritime security is a small part of national security, so the national security practices of a country determine how maritime security practices are in national policy.

3.3. Communication

Edward III's model directs the understanding of policy implementation variables and the relationship between variables by

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determining the role of each variable. Some of the stages of the policy process, which lie between the formulation and consequences that will arise by a policy, are the definition of a policy. Communication has a very important role in the delivery of a policy, this is so that the policies to be conveyed can be understood properly by the implementers. The signing of a contract by the Indonesian government with South Korea worth US \$ 1.1 billion for the purchase of 3 units of the DSME-209 series submarine was carried out in 2011. Equipped with the Improved Changbogo, the DSME-209 submarine is one of the licensed U-209 submarine variants. by South Korea from Germany. The purchase contract states that 1 of the last 3 units of submarines purchased by Indonesia were produced by the National Shipyard, PT. PAL Surabaya. When viewed from a physical point of view, the DSME209 / 1400 Ship is basically a refinement and a marriage of design between the 209/1300 Cakra ship belonging to Indonesia and the submarine type 209/1200 Changbogo belonging to South Korea.[18]

3.4 Human Resources

Means integrated expertise that comes from the thinking and physical power possessed by each person. Those who do and their nature are done still have a close relationship such as descent and their environment, while their work performance is motivated by a desire to fulfill their desires[19]. With regard to human resources, human resources are the main factor in the success of a company's activities in increasing the ability to master technology, especially in the process of transfer of technology for the manufacture and development of submarines carried out by PT. PAL Indonesia from the DSME South Korea tarmac[20]. The age factor is a major gap in the Human Resources sector at PT. PAL Indonesia, where the different personnel who are replaced have a big difference in age[21]. In addition, the readiness of the number of organic human resources of PT. PAL Indonesia is very inadequate, it is inversely proportional to the level of workload faced.[22]

When viewed from the facilities and infrastructure. The South Korean submarine manufacturer is pleased to come to Indonesia and guide PT PAL Indonesia to produce its own submarines[23]. The submarines from South Korea are also of the same quality and sophistication as submarines of their kind. Weighing 1,600 tonnes, the South Korean production submarine is also equipped with torpedoes. In this case, the sophistication of diesel electrified submarines produced by South Korea is relatively the same as other submarines, namely that they must be quiet for a long time, and be equipped with weapons that meet standards[24]. Cooperation between Indonesia and South Korea should prioritize technology transfer schemes to support the independence and advancement of similar domestic industries which are led by PT. PAL Indonesia[25]. There are obstacles and challenges faced in improving the submarine, especially related to the ability of PT. PAL Indonesia is still limited in the manufacture of the DSME 209/1400 submarine[26]. This limitation is due to the fact that Indonesia does not yet have the ability in the field of submarine design, and the infrastructure facilities and infrastructure owned by PT PAL Indonesia itself are not optimal in maintenance, repair, and submarine building activities.[27]

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Although indeed the risk is that our country's waters become open to the crossing of foreign ships, but the most important thing is that the security system must also support so that it can remain able to maintain the unity of the Republic of Indonesia and can also take advantage of its existence[28]. The crossing activities. From the various analyzes carried out, several findings or conclusions were obtained. Indonesia's national interest in the maritime sector consists of three elements, namely the preservation of territorial integrity and state sovereignty, safeguarding maritime resources and domestic and international commercial shipping, and achieving the welfare of the Indonesian nation[29]. Several threats in the region Indonesian waters that need to be a top priority are piracy at sea, illegal fishing, territorial disputes between countries, narcotics smuggling, and people smuggling[30]. Without any strings attached in managing diversity, namely the ability to be able to unite all groups, races and religions, and to be able to unite differences in harmony[31]. This is especially true among elites who based on Indonesian historical aspects are actually actors who used by large countries, both elites from state actors and non-state actors. This is what will bring the Indonesian nation to become a maritime axis country that is respected by other countries[32].

Violations committed in the maritime world must be dealt with quickly, decisively and measurably and transparently in accordance with applicable regulations. Where at this time many provisions have not been implemented so that violations of existing provisions and regulations still occur, especially in the transportation of strategic commodities. Constraints and challenges faced in improving submarines, particularly related to the ability of PT. PAL Indonesia is still limited in the manufacture of the DSME 209/1400 submarine. These limitations are due to: (1) Indonesia does not yet have the ability in the field of submarine design, and the infrastructure facilities and infrastructure owned by PT PAL Indonesia itself are not yet optimal in the maintenance, repair and manufacture of submarines; (2). The human resource capability possessed by PT. PAL Indonesia is still limited and lacks experience in designing submarines, as well as weaknesses in mastering the latest technology

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